

AEROELASTIC RESPONSE OF A TRANSONIC COMPRESSOR CASCADE AT HIGH REDUCED FREQUENCIES

Nenad Glodic
KTH Royal Institute
of Technology
Stockholm, Sweden

**Carlos Tavera
Guerrero**
KTH Royal Institute of
Technology
Stockholm, Sweden

**Mauricio Gutierrez
Salas**
KTH Royal Institute of
Technology
Stockholm, Sweden

ABSTRACT

The present work focuses on experimental and numerical investigations of the unsteady response in a transonic compressor cascade oscillating at high-reduced frequencies. An attempt is made to highlight the main features that drive the unsteady response on the cascade blades. The operating point set in the rig is representative for modern transonic compressors, with a supersonic inflow and oblique shock waves forming at the leading edge of the blades. The cascade consisting of five blades, has been operated in the influence coefficient domain, where the central blade 0 is excited to oscillate in its natural modes of vibration. The investigated modes are mode 3, 4 and 7, with a reduced frequency ranging from 2.08 to 4.55. Steady aerodynamics in the rig has been assessed by measuring the static pressure distributions on the blade and Laser-Two-Focus (L2F) flow field measurements within the central two passages of interest. The aeroelastic testing data indicated that the unsteady blade surface pressure response is mainly driven by the position and relative motion of the shock waves, caused by the blade oscillation. Unsteady response distributions are fairly similar for modes 3 and 4, with some observed differences when compared to mode 7 response. The preliminary results from unsteady simulations qualitatively correspond quite well to the test data, and the main trends are overall well captured both in amplitude and phase. The parametric studies on sensitivity of the numerical solution are ongoing.

Keywords: oscillating cascade, unsteady aerodynamic response, high reduced frequency

NOMENCLATURE

A	blade vibration amplitude	[mm]
c	blade chord	[mm]
\hat{c}_p	complex unsteady pressure coefficient	[-]
f	frequency	[Hz]

k	reduced frequency	[-]
\dot{m}	mass flow	[kg/s]
M_{is}	isentropic Mach number	[-]
p	static pressure	[Pa]
\hat{p}	complex unsteady pressure	[-]
p_0	total pressure	[Pa]
$p_{dyn,ref}$	reference dynamic head	[Pa]
u	flow velocity	[m/s]
γ	stagger angle	[°]

Acronyms

TLC	Transonic Linear Cascade
ARIAS	Advanced Research Into Aeromechanical Solutions
L2F	Laser-Two-Focus
BL	Blade
PS	Pressure Side
SS	Suction Side

1. INTRODUCTION

Accurate determination of aerodynamic damping is crucial in the context of aeromechanical analysis of turbomachinery components. Although significant progress has been made over the past decades when it comes to development of the advanced simulation tools, there is still a need for detailed experimental data for validation of these tools. One of well-established experimental approaches for aerodynamic damping investigation is to measure the aerodynamic response during controlled blade oscillation. This approach provides spatially resolved data, in particular suitable for validation purposes. The tests can either be performed with all the blades oscillating in a traveling wave mode or with only one blade oscillated while the unsteady blade surface pressure is measured on the oscillating blade and neighboring blades, commonly known as influence coefficient approach. Assuming small disturbances and linear

superposition of the unsteady flow these two approaches correlate well for small oscillation amplitudes [1], [2]. The existing cascade facilities around the world are mainly used for controlled flutter testing, where the oscillation frequencies of interest are relatively low (up to several hundred Hz) and the airfoils are usually oscillated in rigid body modes [3]-[8].

The investigation presented in this paper is carried out within the H2020 project ARIAS and it focuses on aerodynamic damping at high reduced frequencies, which is more relevant in the context of forced response analysis. The unsteady blade surface pressure measurements are performed at reduced frequencies of $k \sim 2-4.5$ (based on the full chord), corresponding to mode frequencies in region from ~ 1100 Hz to 2550 Hz. To authors' best knowledge, this has not been addressed anywhere else prior to the present study.

2. METHODOLOGIES

2.1 Experimental setup

The test rig used in the current work is a newly commissioned linear transonic compressor cascade at KTH (Figure 1). The rig contour walls have been designed in a CFD aided method aiming periodic passages adjacent to the central blade by [9]. Further adjustments of the design have been performed to meet the manufacturing and instrumentation requirements. The rig is primarily intended to be used for aerodynamic damping measurements during the blade oscillations at high reduced frequencies and for investigations of aerodynamic damping at near stall flow conditions. The cascade contains five prismatic compressor blade profiles based on the 95% span section of rotor 1 blades from a 3-stage high-speed booster developed within a Swedish national research project called VINK (Virtual Integrated Compressor Demonstrator) [10].

FIGURE 1: TRANSONIC COMPRESSOR CASCADE (TLC) RIG AT KTH

The test rig has a fixed geometry inlet nozzle designed for targeted inlet Mach number of $M=1.22$. To achieve the aerodynamic conditions similar to the reference VINK

compressor blades at nominal speed peak-efficiency, the pitch-to-chord ratio of 0.72 and stagger angle of 65° have also been maintained in the cascade. The flow into the cascade is axial, thus imposing that the blades are staggered with 65 degrees angle with respect to the inlet cross-section. Blade chord is 104.6mm and max thickness is 2.04mm. Given the mass flow limitations (<4.75 kg/s), a blade span height of 70mm is achievable. The tip clearance is set to 0.6mm ($\sim 1\%$ span height). Both sidewalls of the test section are Plexiglas windows, enabling optical access. The blades are mounted on one of the side windows, hereafter referred to as the test section hub.

A schematic view of the test section is shown in Figure 2. To control the periodicity in the cascade, two movable tailboards are implemented, where the lower tailboard also features a smaller adjustable height throttle for control of the backpressure distribution downstream of the blades. In addition, the blades are mounted on a rotatable disc, allowing for incidence angle variability of up to $\pm 8^\circ$. To achieve operating point resembling aerodynamics of the reference VINK compressor blades at peak efficiency, the cascade angle is set to 1.2° providing a mean inflow incidence of $\sim 3.5^\circ$. The operating condition in the cascade is set by controlling the pressure downstream of the cascade with help of tailboards/throttle and suction fans mounted at the far outlet of the wind tunnel piping system (the wind tunnel is operated in an open circuit mode).

FIGURE 2: SCHEMATIC VIEW OF THE CASCADE TEST SECTION

Steady blade loading is measured by means of static pressure taps distributed at 85% span. In total 30 static pressure taps per span position (a pair of two blades each with 15 taps on suction and pressure side respectively) are installed as show in Figure 3. The pressure taps of 0.4mm diameter are connected through the stainless steel tubes to the blade root and further through the vinyl tubes to a quick connector. The steel tubes (0.8mm outer diameter) are embedded in channels milled in the blade surface and are thereafter covered with chemical metal and polished to retrieve a smooth aerodynamic surface.

Inlet and outlet conditions in the test section are described by means of isentropic Mach number distribution, calculated using total pressure measured in the stagnation chamber and the wall static pressures upstream and downstream of the cascade. A total of 28 pressure taps are included on the Plexiglas window that represents the shroud of the test section, as shown in Figure 4. An array of 11 pressure taps (marked with red dots) is located along the pitch direction at 25% chord length upstream of the blades, and another 11 taps are distributed along the pitch at 50%

axial chord length downstream from the blade trailing edge (represented by the blue dots). Time-averaged pressure measurements have been performed employing multichannel PSI9116 pressure scanners with range of $\pm 105\text{KPa}$ at accuracy of $\pm 52.5\text{ Pa}$. Atmospheric pressure has been measured using SOLARTRON barometer with accuracy of $\pm 11.5\text{Pa}$.

FIGURE 3: CASCADE BLADE INSTRUMENTED WITH STATIC PRESSURE TAPS AT 85% SPAN

FIGURE 4: PLEXIGLAS WINDOW INSTRUMENTED WITH THE STATIC PRESSURE TAPS

Flow field measurements of the velocity vectors are performed using non-intrusive anemometer 3D Laser-2-Focus (L2F) system from Polytech (Figure 5). The reference measurement plane for L2F is at 85% span $\pm 0.5\text{mm}$ and is covering passages between blade 0 and its adjacent blades ± 1 . The measurement grid consisted of 148 measurement points per passage. Due to laser light reflections from the blade, the minimum achievable distance from the blade was $\sim 1.5\text{mm}$. During the current measurements the L2F system is used in a 2D mode i.e. for flow velocity and flow angle determination in the plane perpendicular to the laser beams. Small oil droplets are injected upstream of the inlet nozzle, and when they pass two focused laser beams with known foci distance the particles scatter light, which is observed by photo detectors. With the measured time delay between the two impulses, the time-of-flight (TOF) and the particle velocity are calculated. The second focus point is rotated stepwise around the first one to detect the main flow angle. At each step a few hundred to several thousand TOF events are detected for a sufficient statistical analysis. The

obtained flow quantities are the 2D velocity vector magnitude, the flow angle and the turbulence intensity. More details on this technique can be found in [11].

The flow field upstream of the blades is also visualized by means of Schlieren technique, revealing the position of the shock waves when the cascade is operated at transonic conditions. The visualization of the shock wave system in the cascade is in particular useful for qualitative assessment of the flow periodicity in the cascade and to set the correct operating point (OP) in an efficient manner.

FIGURE 5: LASER-2-FOCUS (L2F) SETUP

During the aeroelastic tests, the cascade is operated in the influence coefficient mode i.e. the central blade (blade 0) is vibrating in different mode shapes, while the unsteady response is acquired on both surfaces of the oscillating blade itself and on the adjacent non-oscillating blade surfaces facing toward the oscillating blade (i.e. SS of blade -1 and PS of blade +1). The blade 0 vibration is induced by means of two MFC P1 type (M-2814-P1) piezoelectric actuator elements embedded into pockets milled on the surface of the blade (Figure 7). The piezo-actuators are covered by an elastic filler to maintain a smooth aerodynamic surface. The actuators are supplied with a continuous voltage signal in form of a sinus wave with a maximum amplitude of $\pm 500\text{V}$ and at the frequencies corresponding to the eigen mode frequencies of the blade. For each measurement a frequency sweep was performed and the data is evaluated at the maximum resonant response of the blade. The mode shapes of interest are from mode 3 to mode 7 with frequencies ranging from 1160 Hz to 2530 Hz, which at the targeted aerodynamic operating point corresponds to reduced frequency ranging from ~ 2.08 to 4.55. The reduced frequency is calculated according to Eq.1,

$$k = \frac{2\pi f c}{u} \quad (1)$$

where f denotes the oscillation frequency in [Hz], c the blade chord and u the absolute inlet velocity.

The blade excitation mechanism and detailed characterization of the achieved blade mode shapes are described in [12]. Mode shapes assessed in the current investigation are

modes 3, 4 and 7, depicted in Figure 6. During the rig tests with flow, a shift in mode frequency is observed compared to the no-flow condition. This is believed to be associated to the pre-stress of the blade due to aerodynamic load and slightly different blade clamping boundary conditions due to thermal expansion of the Plexiglas in the presence of the flow. The maximum achievable blade vibration amplitudes in the flow are also significantly lower (up to ~6-8 times lower in some cases) compared to the measured amplitudes when the flow is switched off. The amplitudes are however still sufficient to induce a measurable unsteady pressure response at the surface of the blades.

FIGURE 6: MEASURED BLADE MODE SHAPES INDUCED BY PIEZO-ACTUATORS [11]

The time-resolved blade surface pressure data is measured by using Kulite LQ-160 miniature pressure transducers installed at 85% span section of the blade. The transducers used in the current investigation have a pressure range of 1.7BarA, natural frequency >240 kHz and nonlinearity/repeatability of 0.5% FSO. Even though the transducers are rather small with max. thickness

of 0.65mm, only 8 sensors were possible to install on each blade due to the blade thickness constraints. This type of flat transducers are typically flush mounted with the blade contour, which makes them exposed for mechanical impact and damage during the testing. To protect the sensing element, the Kulite sensors here are mounted on the back-side of the blade profile and are connected to the measurements location through a pressure tap. In that way, a smooth aerodynamic surface is maintained on the measurement location. A small volume (13.3 mm³) exists between the pressure tap and the Kulite membrane (Figure 7) and the mounted sensors were dynamically calibrated to account for potential damping and phase shift of the pressure signal that might arise in the cavity between the pressure tap and sensor membrane. The calibration is done using an in-house built dynamic calibration system as described in [13]. Over the entire range of investigated frequencies (<2600 Hz), the calibration showed only minor influence of the cavity on the unsteady pressure signal (amplitude deviation less than 5% and phase shift of < 4°).

FIGURE 7: INSTALATION OF THE KULITE TRANSDUCERS ON THE OSCILLATING BLADE

To determine the impact of the inertial loads on the transducer diaphragm due to the blade oscillations, the instrumented blades were excited by the piezo actuators inside a vacuum chamber (Figure 8). Since the acceleration is proportional to the frequency square, even for the small vibration amplitudes at the frequencies of interest the transducers are exposed to considerable inertial loads on the diaphragm resulting in relatively high pressure amplitudes readings. Figure 9 shows a sample from the vacuum chamber tests when the instrumented blade was excited at mode 7 with a vibration amplitude of only 0.04mm (amplitude measured at 85% span and 4.8% chord). The

pressure signal amplitudes from the transducers on the vibrating blade were in order of magnitude from 100 to 300Pa at resonance frequency. To be able to correct the pressure readings from the unsteady measurements in the flow, the vacuum response of the instrumented oscillating blades was mapped for all the investigated modes and at the relevant vibration amplitudes corresponding to the ones obtained during the measurements with flow.

FIGURE 8: VACUUM CHAMBER SETUP FOR VIBRATION TESTING OF THE INSTRUMENTED BLADES

FIGURE 9: TRANSDUCER PRESSURE AMPLITUDES MEASURED IN VACUUM; BLADE VIBRATING IN MODE 7

The vibration of the blade 0 inside the TLC rig is monitored by using two single-point high-speed laser vibrometers LK-G152 from Keyence. The vibrometers recover the motion of the blade 0 at 85% span along 4.8% and 41.4% of the chord, as showed schematically in Figure 11. The laser sensor has a maximum sampling frequency of 50 kHz, while the sampling frequency used in the current tests 20 kHz. The linearity of the sensor is $\pm 0.05\%$ of F.S. (F.S. = $\pm 40\text{mm}$) and the repeatability is $0.5\mu\text{m}$. The unsteady pressure data and laser signals are acquired using a high-speed data acquisition system SLICE PRO SIM from DTS. The system features 18 channels with 16bit A/D conversion for each channel and a maximum sampling rate for

all 18 channels simultaneously of 500kps/ch. The present tests were performed at a sampling rate of 50kps.

2.1 Numerical model

In addition to the experiments, corresponding numerical simulations of the rig tests are carried out in ANSYS CFX 2021 R2 using time-marching 3D viscous model. The simulations are conducted using a standard SST turbulence model. The motion of the oscillating blade is imposed by a moving mesh boundary condition. The mode shapes obtained from Ansys Mechanical are projected onto the CFD mesh of the blade zero and the mode frequency is corresponding to the frequency measured during the experiments. The maximum amplitude is set to 0.25 mm. The mesh employed in the study is a multi-block type mesh containing both O- and H-blocks, generated using ICM CFD meshing tool. The computational domain consists of two contractions, one convergent-divergent nozzle and the test section, as indicated in Figure 12. The mesh has in total $\sim 4.7\text{M}$ hexahedral elements with a $y^+ \approx 2.5$ at the blades. The simulation domain is consistent with the experimental setup (cross-section shown in Figure 11), allowing for relevant comparison between experimental and numerical results. As a boundary condition in the simulations, the total pressure and total temperature at the inlet of the domain were set to the same values as measured in the rig, while the outlet static pressure was adjusted to match the pressure ratio from the experiment. During the transient simulations, the time period is discretized with 40 time-steps per oscillation period. Convergence is assumed when the properties of interest (pressure monitor points on the blade surface) display less than 1% variation in harmonic amplitudes over the last two periods, which is typically achieved after 10 to 12 oscillation periods, depending on the analyzed mode.

FIGURE 11: CROSS-SECTION OF THE TLC RIG

FIGURE 12: CFD SIMULATION DOMAIN

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Steady state aerodynamics

In the present investigation, the inlet Mach number was 1.2 and the pressure ratio between the downstream static pressure and the upstream static pressure was 1.405. The set flow condition was such that the oblique shock waves formed on the blades 0 and ± 1 were slightly detached from the blade leading edge, as visualized by Schlieren technique in Figure 13. These bow shock waves are impinging on the suction side of the neighboring blade at around 60-65% chord (depending on the blade index). However, this could not be visualized by Schlieren since the blade platforms are blocking the light beams in the passage region between the blades. In addition to the observed LE bow shock, a weaker lip shock wave (expansion wave) is formed behind the expansion region on the LE of the blades 0 and ± 1 . The lip shock wave is considerably stronger on blade -2, caused by the high flow acceleration around the leading edge of the blade -2. The actual detached bow shock wave initially formed on this blade has been pushed quite far upstream from the blade -2 LE and is therefore not visible in the section visualized by Schlieren. Since being pushed upstream, this blade -2 shock wave is rather transformed to a normal shock wave causing strong deceleration of the flow across the inlet cross section upstream of the blades. The flow then re-accelerates to transonic velocities once it reaches the LE of blade -2. Limited extent of the cascade and proximity of the upper wall causes also that the shockwaves are reflecting from the inclined upper wall and the weak reflected shocks are to a certain extent impinging back on the blades. The presence of the described shock wave structure in the cascade is central for understanding the unsteady pressure fluctuations on the blade surfaces.

FIGURE 13: SCHLIEREN VISUALIZATION OF THE SHOCK WAVES IN THE CASCADE

L2F measurements of the Mach number at 85% span section together with the corresponding numerical results shown in Figure 14, provide an insight in the flow field within the blade passages formed by blade 0 and its adjacent blades. These two central passages are also in focus during the aeroelastic measurements. The contour plots shows that qualitatively there is a fairly good agreement between the experimental and

computed velocity field. Both results show that the bow shock formed at the LE of blade 0 has an oblique shape and impinges on the suction side of the blade -1 at around 65% chord. At this span height the passage flow downstream of that shock is also dominated by the low momentum flow associated by the tip leakage vortex. On the PS of the blade 0 close to the LE a limited region exists where the flow is accelerated to transonic and again decelerated through a short-extent shock wave formed there. On the PS of the blade +1, this transonic region downstream of the LE is much less pronounced and no clear shock could be observed. The shock wave formed at the blade +1 LE seems to be less inclined and is closer to a normal shock, thus imposing slightly stronger deceleration gradient in that passage. This shock impinges on the suction side of the blade 0 around 60% chord. The shock predicted by CFD appears to be somewhat stronger compared to the one retrieved from the L2F measurements.

FIGURE 14: L2F MEASURED AND CFD PREDICTED MACH NUMBER DISTRIBUTION AT 85% SPAN

Figure 15 displays the isentropic Mach number against the normalized pitch, upstream and downstream of the blades. The plot includes also corresponding CFD simulation results. Both experimental and CFD values indicate that there is a clear increase in the upstream Mach number going from the negative

blade passages towards the positive pitch in the cascade. The values are increasing from ~ 1.1 to ~ 1.25 upstream of the blade +1. The outlier lower Mach number point far to the left in the graph (at pitchwise coordinate $= -1.6$) is actually in the region where the flow has not yet been re-accelerated to transonic. The observed local dips in Mach numbers are associated with the location of the LE shock wave extensions, and are fairly well captured by the CFD. The predicted Mach number values upstream of the blade +1 seem to be lower than the ones measured in the rig. The predicted downstream values are in a relative good agreement with the measured ones in the region downstream of the blades 0 and +1, while downstream of the blade -1 simulation results show higher values as moving further towards negative pitch.

FIGURE 15: UPSTREAM AND DOWNSTREAM ISENTROPIC MACH DISTRIBUTION

The steady blade loading in Figure 16 is displayed in form of isentropic Mach number distributions at the 85% span section of the blade 0 and adjacent blade surfaces facing towards blade 0 (BL+1 PS and BL -1 SS). It can be observed that the steady blade loading is not fully periodic, which could already be anticipated from the above described flow conditions. The most obvious differences are observed on the suction side of the blades 0 and -1, where different positions of the shock are noted. Upstream of the shock, blade 0 exhibits higher Mach number compared to blade -1. CFD prediction captures well the position of the shock, but under-predicts the Mach number values upstream of the shock. The differences between the values on the blade 0 and blade -1 fore suction side are also visible in the simulations. CFD captures quite well also the shock on the fore part of the blade 0 pressure side.

FIGURE 16: STEADY BLADE LOADING AT 85% SPAN

During the experiments, a static blade deflection of around 0.9 mm was recorded by the laser vibrometers. This static displacement induced by the steady aerodynamic loads was not included in the CFD geometry, and thus could be a possible source contributing to the observed differences between the CFD and experiments. Another detail that was not included in the modelled geometry was a small gap that exists between the blade -2 TE and lower tailboard, and between the blade +2 TE and upper tailboard respectively. For the investigated operating point, the lower tailboard was aligned with the blade +2 TE, but due to static deformation of the blade there was a gap present. The gap was even slightly larger on the upper tailboard since it was set to an angle of -0.3 degrees relative to the cascade angle (rotated in counter clockwise direction relative to its pivot), which opened the gap a bit further. It has been noted in the experiments that the operating point and the flow field in the cascade was highly sensitive to the tailboard angle settings and by that also likely sensitive to the change in the actual bleed opening between the blade TE and the tailboard.

Since the periodicity of the steady flow field in the cascade is not fully achieved, the assumption of the influence coefficient method that the travelling wave mode and by that an overall aerodamping value can be estimated from the superposition of the individual influence coefficient, is not valid any more. However, the achieved flow conditions are still considered relevant and the testing with the oscillating blade are justified since the goal here is rather to analyze the unsteady pressure response locally on the blades and to provide detailed unsteady pressure data for validation purposes.

3.2 Unsteady pressure data

The unsteady surface pressures on the blades are presented in form of amplitude and phase of the complex unsteady pressure coefficient relative to the blade motion. The time-resolved pressure signals are reduced to complex pressures by Fourier transformation at the oscillation frequency and are thereafter

normalized by the reference dynamic head and the oscillation amplitude as follows

$$\hat{C}_p = \frac{\hat{p} \cdot c}{A \cdot p_{dyn,ref}} \quad (2)$$

The blade vibration amplitude A is measured by the laser vibrometer at 4.8% chord from the blade LE and the reference dynamic head $p_{dyn,ref}$ is obtained from the total pressure measured in the settling chamber and averaged upstream static pressure measurements. In addition, the pressure amplitudes measured on the oscillating blade are corrected by subtracting the pressure amplitudes measured in vacuum, to account for the acceleration loads on the transducers.

3.2.1 Mode 3

Figure 17 shows the unsteady response at 85 % span section of the blades 0 and ± 1 , when blade 0 is vibrating in mode 3 at 1160 Hz which corresponds to a reduced frequency of $k=2.08$. The measured vibration amplitude was 0.037 mm. In this chord-wise bending mode, the maximum deformation is observed near the leading and trailing edge of the blade. The unsteady pressure on the oscillating blade 0 features high amplitude in the vicinity of the blade LE, probably driven by the localized blade deformation interacting with the lip shock wave formed at the LE. On the PS around 20% chord, a second peak is observed associated with the location of the local short-extent passage shock wave, seen in Mach number distribution in Figure 14. On the blade 0 SS, an amplitude peak is noted at around 60% chord. This is the location where the oblique shock wave coming from the blade +1 LE impinges and interacts with the SS boundary layer on blade 0. This shock wave is moving driven by the blade 0 oscillation. Similar amplitude peak is measured on the SS of blade -1, which in its turn is caused by the blade 0 LE shock wave.

The position of the unsteady pressure peak on blade -1 is shifted downstream compared to the peak observed on the SS of blade 0. This is probably due to the fact that the strength and angle of the oblique shocks on blades 0 and +1 are slightly different from each other, as the steady flow field is not fully periodic. These unsteady pressure peaks seem to be associated with a shift in the pressure phase angle. The numerical prediction captures well the main trends of the measured pressure amplitudes both on the blade 0 and blade -1, even though some local differences can be observed e.g. on the aft part of the blade 0 pressure side. The phase angle of the pressure response for this mode is very well predicted on all three blades, except for the last two measurement locations on the blade 0 suction side, downstream of the shock wave.

FIGURE 17: UNSTEADY BLADE LOADING AT 85% SPAN, MODE 3 @ 1160 Hz ($k=2.08$)

Response measured on the blade +1 PS is of a moderate character, with a quite monotonic increase in amplitudes towards the leading edge. CFD predicts elevated pressure amplitudes in the region between 15 and 40% chord, which was not observed

in the experiments. The unsteady pressure has not been measured on the blade +1 suction side, but the simulation results indicate a distinct high response peak around 60% chord even though the SS is facing away from the oscillating blade. It is believed that this high unsteadiness is due to a detached normal shock formed on the blade +2 LE. This shock wave also interacts with the reflection of the blade 0 bow shock wave from the upper wall, and modulated with the blade 0 vibration frequency it is impinging and causing the unsteadiness on the blade +1 SS.

3.2.2 Mode 4

Figure 18 shows the unsteady response for mode 4 at 1550 Hz, corresponding to a reduced frequency $k = 2.79$. The measured vibration amplitude was 0.08 mm. The maximum deformation in this mode is localized near the LE and close to the tip, as seen in Figure 6. Similar to what was observed for mode 3, pressure fluctuations are mainly induced at the locations where the shocks are interacting with the blade surface boundary layers. The peak region at the fore PS of the blade 0 is more pronounced than what it was for the mode 3, probably due to localized larger deformation of the blade in mode 4. The unsteady pressure peak on the SS of the blade 0 is less pronounced for this mode.

The CFD results are in quite good agreement with the measured data, and trends both in amplitude and phase seem to be captured well by the simulations. The measured peak on the blade -1 suction side seems to be somewhat stronger than what was observed for mode 3 and is shifted more towards the trailing edge, which is also partially observed in the CFD. Predicted response on the blade +1 PS matches quite well measured data and both indicate a region of elevated pressure amplitudes between the leading edge and ~25% chord.

FIGURE 18: UNSTEADY BLADE LOADING AT 85% SPAN, MODE 4 @ 1550 Hz ($k=2.79$)

3.2.1 Mode 7

The unsteady pressure response acquired for mode 7 at 2530Hz (corresponding to a reduced frequency $k=4.55$), is shown in Figure 19. The measured vibration amplitude was 0.028 mm. The amplitude of the response for mode 7 seems to be overall higher than for modes 3 & 4, and for all three blades of interest. The amplitude distribution on the blade 0 PS is different compared to what was measured for modes 3 and 4, and a high response is observed in the aft region from 40% chord to the trailing edge. This is also well captured by CFD.

A slightly different response could also be observed on the blade 0 SS, where the pressure fluctuations appear to be more pronounced than for the previous two modes and there is a clear increase in pressure unsteadiness towards the trailing edge. CFD results are in agreement with the experimental ones, and the overall trend is well predicted. Differences are observed on the PS of blade +1 where CFD predicts higher response along the whole pressure side except for the fore part where larger peak amplitude was measured. The phase of the response seem to be captured very well by CFD on blades 0 and +1, while some discrepancies exist on the blade -1 SS.

FIGURE 19: UNSTEADY BLADE LOADING AT 85% SPAN, MODE 7 @ 2530 Hz ($k=4.55$)

4. CONCLUSIONS

A first set of measurement data obtained in KTH's transonic compressor cascade oscillating at high reduced frequencies is presented. The cascade consisting of five blades has been operated in the influence coefficient domain, where the central blade is excited to oscillate in its natural modes of vibration. The investigated modes are mode 3, 4 and 7, with a reduced frequency ranging from 2.08 to 4.55. Unsteady blade surface pressure data has been acquired on 85% span section and the passages of interest are those adjacent to blade zero.

The operating point set in the rig is representative for modern transonic compressors, with supersonic inflow and oblique shock waves forming at the leading edge of the blades. Steady aerodynamics has been assessed by means of steady blade loading measurements and L2F flow field measurements within the two passages of interest. Schlieren visualization provides an insight in the shock wave structure upstream of the blades. Due to limited extent of the cascades, the flow is not fully periodic leading to slightly different flow structures in the investigated passages. A comparison to initial CFD steady aerodynamic results highlighted the regions where the differences with experiments were observed. Further assessment of sensitivity of numerical solutions to the level of detailing included in the model will have to be carried out.

The unsteady pressure data from aeroelastic testing indicated that the unsteady response on the blade surface is mainly driven by the position and relative motion of the shock waves, caused by the blade oscillation. When impinging on the blade surface these oscillating shocks interact with the boundary layer and cause locally strong fluctuations in pressure. Three regions with elevated pressure amplitudes were identified: a) region in a direct vicinity of the blade leading edge, where the flow re-accelerates to transonic behind the slightly detached LE shock and where a weak lip shock wave forms, b) region on the aft suction side where the oblique shock coming from the adjacent blade LE impinges onto the blade surface and c) region on the fore pressure side of the oscillating blade where an additional localized shock wave exists and is driven by the local deformation of the blade. Unsteady response distributions are fairly similar for modes 3 and 4, with some observed differences in the extent of amplitude peaks. Meanwhile mode 7 displays somewhat stronger response towards the aft part of both pressure side and suction side of the blade 0.

The preliminary results from unsteady simulations qualitatively correspond quite well to the test data, and the main trends are well captured both in amplitude and phase. The parametric studies on sensitivity of the numerical solution are ongoing.

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